

RESEARCH ON INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION STYLES IN PEDAGOGICAL TEAMS

Taukelova Gulnaziya Esengeldiqzy

Senior Lecturer at the Khoja Ahmed Yasawi International Kazakh-Turkish University,
Turkistan, Kazakhstan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15273485>

Annotation. *This article examines the psychological climate of the pedagogical staff in the field of education. Based on special experimental studies, the state of interpersonal relationships within the pedagogical team is determined, indicating that teachers perceive their professional environment as having a positive psychological climate. Additionally, the significance of teacher’s communication styles in influencing the psychological climate of the team is emphasized. Since the dominant communication styles among the members of the pedagogical team are submissive, friendly, and altruistic, it is suggested that the overall psychological well-being of the team is also at a high level.*

Keywords: *pedagogical team, psychological climate, interpersonal communication styles, psychological well-being.*

The psychological climate in any team is characterized and manifested by the interpersonal communication features of the people within the group. Indeed, psychological climate (from the Greek word klima (klimatos) “slope”) is a set of psychological conditions that influence the comprehensive development of an individual and their productive activity within the group, as well as the qualitative aspect of interpersonal relationships. Therefore, the positivity in interpersonal relationships within the team contributes to the team’s professional productivity and the psychological well-being of its members. In this regard, the manifestations of the psychological well-being of the team are characterized by the following important qualities.

- The trust and high expectations among team members;
- Positive and businesslike criticism;
- The freedom to express one’s opinion during discussions of issues concerning the entire team;
- Leaders not exerting pressure on subordinates and allowing for group decision-making;
- Team members being fully informed about their duties and work status;
- Confidence in the full integration of team members into the group;
- Each team member taking responsibility for tasks according to their role in the team.

In the current era of scientific-technological and social progress, there is a noticeable continuous complication of business communication among people during the process of action. Along with this, the role of psychological factors in interpersonal communication within labor teams is also growing exponentially. This issue is not excluded from pedagogical teams. Faith Zabek and others, in their studies, indicate that due to the lack of multi-level methods applied in climate research in schools, it raises doubts about the accuracy and consistency of indicators regarding the psychological climate in schools. Therefore, inter-school comparisons of climate

may not be reliable, as the climate at the school level is constantly changing, and this area of research is still not fully explored.

The teacher and leader personality within a pedagogical team determine the positive climate in a school. The human factor in the school consists of the psychological and socio-psychological characteristics of leaders and teachers. These include their interests, desires, aspirations, expectations from one another, behavioral traits and abilities, accumulated knowledge, skills, and expertise. These elements reflect the psychological traits and state of the pedagogical team, its mood, creative and moral microclimate, integrity, labor and managerial activity, psychological harmony, prestige, and so on. Therefore, the establishment of a positive psychological climate in the pedagogical team is essential for cooperative creative work and for positively resolving conflicts.

The professional duty of a teacher is not easy during the process of growth, one must actively influence the structure of the individual's personality. The issues related to the psychological climate in the pedagogical team have been studied by scientists such as V.I. Andreyev, D.A. Belukhin, R.G. Mamed-zade, T.V. Mishatkina, V.I. Pisarenko, I.Ya. Pisarenko, P.K. Kholmogorzev, V.N. Chernokozova, I.I. Chernokozov, and others.

In any team, when a social-psychological climate is established, it can have a positive or negative impact on the members of the team. Mutual consultation and cooperative relationships allow both experienced and young teachers to find shared joy in a united team. However, when indifference, apathy, or pressure dominate, a team member becomes demotivated and feels oppressed, which can lead to a decrease in the productivity of their work, the emergence of conflicts, or even a decision to move to another team.

In general, a team refers to a unity of individuals who interact with one another and recognize themselves as part of a group, acknowledging their belonging to this social unit from the perspective of others. The main climatic condition of a pedagogical team is reflected in its solidarity. Solidarity is an integrative social-psychological characteristic attributed to the pedagogical team. Naturally, factors that hinder the formation of a positive psychological climate include social-psychological disagreements within the team or the escalation of contradictions arising from direct interpersonal conflicts. In professional pedagogical activity, factors that obstruct the achievement of goals include the level of professional competence and the mismatch of behavior with the norms of interpersonal interaction.

The mood within a team, public opinion, emotional energy, and the level of interpersonal relationships are determined by the social-psychological environment established within the team. The substantive characteristics of the psychological climate in the team are defined by the interactions among team members, their mood, satisfaction with the processes of joint work, the quality of this work, and most importantly, the conditions created for their professional self-growth. A positive social-psychological environment in a pedagogical team provides moral and psychological strength, and is characterized by responsibility, respect, high expectations, and vigilance. Henrik Nordahl and others, in their article Metacognition, cognition and social anxiety: A test of temporal and reciprocal relationships, identify the characteristics of interpersonal interactions based on a person's metacognitive beliefs, social self-beliefs, and signs of social anxiety.

In the course of pedagogical work, some teachers are able to understand and tolerate the emotional states of their colleagues, while others tend to analyze their psychological conditions and compare them to their own beliefs and inclinations. Long-term collaboration and shared

interests significantly facilitate the process of positive imitation. Recognizing and understanding the emotional mood of colleagues, as well as sharing thoughts on the matter, is optimal. The two sides of interaction consist of the individual’s perception of the team’s environment. Teachers who are responsible, sociable, kind, polite, and considerate of fairness can make a significant contribution to creating a positive environment in the team. Conversely, an impolite, disorganized, and less understanding team member can contribute to creating a negative “atmosphere.” The overall climate of the team depends on the intelligence, responsibility, and other emotional-intellectual characteristics of its members, as well as the psychological well-being of each educator. Some individual teachers’ cognitive activity and creativity can drive the team towards innovative activities, pushing for the exploration of new technologies. A motivated teacher-leader can inspire others to follow their example. If the minds, emotions, and willpower of the team members are focused on pedagogical activity, success is not difficult to achieve.

The objective of the experimental study was to determine the psychological well-being of the pedagogical team and the interpersonal communication styles of teachers in secondary schools in the city of Turkestan. Based on this, the task was set to test the hypothesis that the interpersonal communication style of teachers affects the level of psychological climate in the pedagogical team.

For the diagnostic study, the “Psychological Climate in the Group” express methodology and T. Liri’s diagnostic methodology of interpersonal communication were selected. The goal of the first methodology was to study the psychological climate within a small group, while the goal of the second methodology was to identify the predominant type of attitude towards people in teachers’ self-assessment and interpersonal observation.

The types of interpersonal relationships according to T. Liri are as follows:

1. Observer type
2. Authoritative (domineering) type
3. Egoistic type
4. Aggressive type
5. Doubtful type
6. Submissive type
7. Dependent type
8. Warm-hearted type
9. Altruistic type

Diagram 1. Results obtained using the Psychological Climate in the Group express methodology.

As seen from the table, 50% of the participants assessed the level of psychological climate in the pedagogical team as positive, 30% as negative, and 20% of the participants assessed the level of psychological climate in the pedagogical team as average.

Diagram 2. Interpersonal communication styles of pedagogical team members according to T. Liri’s methodology.

As seen from the diagram, all types of interpersonal communication styles of the participants are displayed at an average or low level, indicating their adaptive behavior patterns.

In the pedagogical team, the altruistic (8) and warm-hearted (7.7) communication styles are clearly evident. These styles reflect the teachers’ willingness to cooperate, collaborate, align with the views of others, and demonstrate responsibility and kindness. The submissive type (7.6) indicates the teacher’s emotional restraint, ability to obey, and dedication to performing their duties with integrity. Since the authoritarian communication style (6.9) is observed at a low level, it shows that while the teacher may not be a leader, they still exhibit self-confidence and high adaptability in establishing cooperation. Correspondingly, the lowest levels of interpersonal communication styles are seen in the aggressive (5.6) and dependent (6.1) types. However, analyzing the diagram, we observe that the teachers generally express conformity and kindness in their interactions with the team, often adapting to the viewpoints of others. The lowest levels are found in the egoistic (4.3) and doubtful (4) styles. This reflects a low level of focus on their own persona and a lack of confidence in the team.

Conclusion. Based on theoretical and experimental studies, we attempted to identify the relationship between the level of psychological climate in the pedagogical team and the interpersonal communication styles of the teachers. To achieve the research goal, it was necessary to focus on the concepts of pedagogical communication, the psychological climate of the team, individual styles, and the teacher’s personality. Summarizing the results of the two methodologies conducted on the participants, we found that 50% of the participants rated the psychological climate in the pedagogical team as high. Meanwhile, 20% and 30% of the remaining participants assessed the psychological climate in the team as average and negative, respectively. Taking these results into account, we concluded that, based on the research findings, the predominant interpersonal communication styles among the pedagogical team members are submissive, warm-hearted, and altruistic.

Thus, the psychological climate in the pedagogical teams of schools in the city of Turkestan is relatively positive. This is directly related to the interpersonal communication styles of the pedagogical team members. In other words, the team members demonstrate a predominant

orientation towards congruence (confrontation) and conformity in their interpersonal relationships within the social environment.

REFERENCES

1. Faith Zabek et al. Can a school climate survey accurately and equitably measure school quality? Examining the multilevel structure and invariance of the Georgia School Climate Scale. *Journal of School Psychology*, № 95 (2022) P. 1–24.
2. Henrik Nordahl et al. Metacognition, cognition and social anxiety: A test of temporal and reciprocal relationships. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders* 86 (2022) 102516
3. Anikeeva N.P. Psychological climate in the collective. Moscow, “Prosveshchenie”, 1989.
4. Grekhnev V.S. The culture of pedagogical communication. Moscow, “Prosveshchenie”, 1990.
5. Ilyusizova S.M. Teacher and student: issues of relationships. Almaty, “Mektep”, 1989.
6. Kolesnikov L.F. Reserves of pedagogical labor efficiency. Novosibirsk, 1985.
7. Tambovtseva T.S. Research on the individual style of pedagogical communication. *Journal “Questions of Psychology”*, Moscow, 1990, No. 5.